

Deep water

Varietal improvement of photosensitive types for medium-deep areas

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Much of the riceland in South and Southeast Asia is planted to photoperiod-sensitive varieties of medium to late duration (150–170 days) whose flowering times coincide with the post-monsoon period from mid-October to late November. More than 60 percent of India's riceland is in such varieties.

The early, photoperiod-sensitive, high-yielding varieties are not considered suitable for such areas. Badly needed are high-yielding lines that have different photosensitive periods, are adapted to low light intensity and poor drainage, and are resistant to insects and diseases.

Since high levels of crop management are not possible during the monsoon period, such varieties should yield better than traditional tall varieties now being grown with moderate fertilization and pest control.

For waterlogged areas, highly productive, photoperiod-sensitive, and nonlodging medium-tall varieties should be developed. Such lines have been bred at CRRI by utilizing Jagannath and Pankaj. Particularly promising are lines from the crosses Pankaj/Jagannath, CR70/Pankaj, and Pankaj/Kada, and from Jagannath natural crosses. These lines yielded from 4 to 6 t/ha with average management, minimum plant protection, and low levels of nitrogen (20–40 kg N/ha). Improved late-maturing types now cultivated in India are Mahsuri, CR 1014, Pankaj, and Jagannath.

Lines from the cross Pankaj/Jagannath made at the Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, Orissa state, India, are particularly promising.

Temperature tolerance

Varietal reactions to high temperature

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Sixty-eight varieties were screened for tolerance to high temperatures under day/night temperature regimes of 35°/27°C in the IRRI phytotron.

Interestingly, all varieties identified as tolerant were upland varieties, and six of seven were resistant or moderately resistant to drought under field conditions. The findings suggest that heat and desiccation tolerance (in part) share a common mechanism.

IR8 was more tolerant of high temperature than were the other IRRI varieties tested. Such temperature tolerance may partly explain why IR8 has been successful in regions of Pakistan where high temperatures prevail.

List of high temperature-tolerant and susceptible varieties. IRRI, 1975.

Variety	Fertility at high temperature (%)
<i>Tolerant</i>	
Agbede	88
Carreon	90
Dular	86
N22	92
OS 4	86
PI 215936	88
Sintiane Diofor	86
IR8	78
<i>Susceptible</i>	
Basmati-370	4
BKN 6624-46-2	3
C4-63G	8
H4	2
Pelita I/1	7

IRRI's phytotron was used to screen 68 rice varieties for tolerance to high temperatures. Seven upland varieties were identified as tolerant. The phytotron, a gift of the Australian Government, has 32 controlled environment areas; it is used by scientists of various disciplines.